

INVESTIGATION AND MOLECULAR DOCKING STUDIES ON SECONDARY METABOLITES OBTAINED FROM *BEAUVERIA BASSIANA* AGAINST HEXAMERIN RECEPTOR PROTEIN OF *CORCYRA CEPHALONICA*, STORED PRODUCT PEST

S. Nagalakshmi*, B. Seethalakshmi

Assistant Professor, Department of Zoology, Queen Mary's College, Chennai- 600 004.

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*Corresponding Author

S. Nagalakshmi

Assistant Professor, Department of
Zoology, Queen Mary's College,
Chennai- 600 004.

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Entomopathogenic fungi are rich sources of bioactive secondary metabolites that possess insecticidal properties. The present study reported a novel approach for the identification of insecticidal compounds produced by *Beauveria bassiana* and to assess their toxicity against the rice moth *Corcyra cephalonica*. Only few studies were focused on the compound Beauveriolide-V, produced during the infection of *B. bassiana*. These studies were evaluated the pathogenicity of insect pest and limited information of Beauveriolide-V from entomopathogenic fungi such as *B. bassiana*. They also lack the information on dynamic role of secondary metabolites during the parthenogenesis and fungal development in in-vivo insect host. **Methods:** our study is the first to report the molecular docking of Beauveriolide-V against the insect pest *C. cephalonica*. Furthermore the ligand target interaction of secondary metabolite of *B. bassiana* with target insect

hexamerin receptor protein predicted the role of toxicity against insect pest. This novel approach provides a potential impact of biological control and molecular docking studies forms the ultimate information whether the toxic protein of the biopesticide binds with the insect protein. **Results:** The docking score between the fungal metabolite Beauveriolide V and the target protein was -10.941kcal/mol and the fungal metabolite Tenellin showed -12.191kcal/mol. The glide energy obtained was about -51.77 for Beauveriolide V and -54.486

for Tenellin respectively. **Conclusion:** From the results it is suggested that *B. bassiana* culture filtrates will be used against the *C. cephalonica* larvae as a biocontrol agent.

KEYWORDS: *Beauveria bassiana*, docking, *Corcyra*, biopesticide.

INTRODUCTION

Insect pests are a major constraint to increased global production of food and fiber. Biological control agents including arthropod natural enemies, entomopathogens (bacteria, nematode, virus, and fungus), plant-derived insecticides and insect hormones are receiving significant interest as alternatives to chemical pesticides and as key components of integrated pest management system. Biotechnology has a significant role in improving efficacy, cost-effectiveness and in expanding the markets for these bioinsecticides.

The span of agriculturally important insect pests which can be targeted by the fungal entomopathogens which are formulated as microbial bio-pesticides includes leaf feeding caterpillars (eg. *Spodoptera litura*), internal feeding larval stages (like sugarcane early shoot borer) besides soil dwelling larval stages (like white grubs), sedentary sucking pest (like scale insects and mealy bugs), besides actively dispersing sucking pests (like thrips and hoppers).

Entomopathogenic fungi are rich sources of bioactive secondary metabolites that possess insecticidal properties. The present study reported a novel approach for the identification of insecticidal compounds produced by *Beauveria bassiana* and to assess their toxicity against the rice moth *Corcyra cephalonica*. Only few studies were focused on the compound Beauveriolide-V, produced during the infection of *B. bassiana*. These studies were evaluated the pathogenicity of insect pest and limited information of Beauveriolide-V from entomopathogenic fungi such as *B. bassiana*. They also lack the information on dynamic role of secondary metabolites during the parthenogenesis and fungal development in in-vivo insect host. Hence, our study is the first to report the molecular docking of Beauveriolide-V against the insect pest *C. cephalonica*. Furthermore the ligand target interaction of secondary metabolite of *B. bassiana* with target insect hexamerin receptor protein predicted the role of toxicity against insect pest. This novel approach provides a potential impact of biological control and molecular docking studies forms the ultimate information whether the toxic protein of the biopesticide binds with the insect protein.

OBJECTIVES

In view of the above findings the present study is aimed to investigate the following aspects.

1. Retrieval of target protein hexamerin receptor protein from GenBank(NCBI).
2. Retrieval of ligand (secondary metabolites) structures through PubChem from NCBI.
3. To identify homology modeling of target protein of other insects.
4. Molecular docking of secondary metabolites from *B. bassiana* against the hexamerin receptor protein of the stored product pest, *C. cephalonica*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Selection of Protein target

Hexamerins are multifunctional insect storage proteins utilized during metamorphosis of holometabolous insects. These proteins are stage specifically taken up by the fat body cells from the haemolymph due to receptor-mediated endocytosis. The hexamerin receptor and the concomitant hexamerin sequestration in the rice moth *Corcyra cephalonica* is controlled by the steroid hormone 20-hydroxy-ecdysone (20E)(Arif *et al.*, 2003). The process of uptake of hexamerins during metamorphosis from insect haemolymph by fat body cells is reminiscent of receptor-mediated endocytosis. Budatha *et al.* (2011) identified a hexamerin-binding protein (HBP) and reported for the first time that uptake of hexamerins is dependent on the phosphorylation of HBP partly by a tyrosine kinase, which is, in turn, activated by 20-hydroxyecdysone (20E). However, the exact nature of HBP and the mechanism of interaction are still unknown.

In the present study hexamerin receptor of *c. cephalonica* is selected as a target protein against the following fungal *B. bassiana* secondary metabolites.

- i. Bassianin
- ii. Beavericin
- iii. Beauveriolide I
- iv. Beauveriolide III
- v. Beauveriolide IV
- vi. Beauveriolide V
- vii. Oosporein
- viii. Tenellin

Tools used for retrieval of target protein and secondary metabolites structure

PubChem

PubChem (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>) is a public repository for information on chemical substances and their biological activities. PubChem is a component of the Molecular Libraries. For the past 11 years, PubChem has grown to a sizable system, serving as a chemical information resource for the scientific research community. PubChem consists of three inter-linked databases, Substance, Compound and BioAssay. The Substance database contains chemical information deposited by individual data contributors to PubChem, and the Compound database stores unique chemical structures extracted from the Substance database. Biological activity data of chemical substances tested in assay experiments are contained in the BioAssay database.

In the present study the structure of secondary metabolites of entomopathogenic fungi *B. bassiana* were retrieved from PubChem and converted to mol format.

Protein data bank

The Protein Data Bank (PDB) archive is the single worldwide repository of information about the 3D structures of large biological molecules, including proteins and nucleic acids. These are the molecules of life that are found in all organisms including bacteria, yeast, plants, flies, other animals, and humans. The structures in the archive range from tiny proteins and bits of DNA to complex molecular machines like the ribosome. The PDB archive is available at no cost to users. The crystallographic structure of hexamerin receptor protein of *C. cephalonica* was retrieved from protein data bank (PDB).

Homology modeling

Homology modeling is an *insilico* technique which as an advantage of building the protein molecules. Major goal of structural biology involve formation of protein-ligand complexes; in which the protein molecules act energetically in the course of binding. Therefore, perceptive of protein-ligand interaction will be very important for structure based drug design. Lack of knowledge of 3D structures has hindered efforts to understand the binding specificities of ligands with protein. With increasing in modeling software and the growing number of known protein structures, homology modeling is rapidly becoming the method of choice for obtaining 3D coordinates of proteins.

Homology modeling is the computational approaches for protein three-dimensional structure modeling and prediction. Homology modeling builds an atomic model based on experimentally determined known structures that have sequence homology of more than 40%. It is also known as comparative modeling.

Homology modeling technique relaxes the tough requirement of force field and enormous conformation searching, because it deals with the calculation of a force field and replaces it in large part, with the counting of sequence identities. The method is based on the fact that structural conformation of a protein is more highly conserved than its amino acid sequence, and that small or medium changes in sequence normally result in little variation in the 3D structure.

SwissModel

SwissModel is accessible via a web server that accepts the sequence to be modeled, and then delivers the model by an electronic mail Guex and Peitsch 1997. In contrast to Modeller, SwissModel follows the standard protocol of homologue identification, sequence alignment, determining the core backbone and modeling loops and side chains. SwissModel will search a sequence database of proteins in the PDB with BLAST, and will attempt to build a model for any PDB hits.

Molecular docking

Molecular docking was performed using induced fit docking method using Schrodinger software.

Induced Fit Docking

The active site geometry of a protein complex depends heavily upon conformational changes induced by the bound ligand. However, resolving the crystallographic structure of a protein-ligand complex requires a substantial investment of time, and is frequently infeasible or impossible. Schrödinger's Induced Fit (IFD) protocol solves this problem by using Glide and Prime to exhaustively consider possible binding modes and the associated conformational changes within receptor active sites. The unique procedure allows chemists to quickly predict active site geometries with minimal expense, even for systems as challenging as hERG homology models.

The Induced Fit protocol begins by docking the active ligand with Glide. In order to generate a diverse ensemble of ligand poses, the procedure uses reduced van der Waals radii and an increased Coulomb-vdw cut off, and can temporarily remove highly flexible side chains during the docking step. For each pose, a Prime structure prediction is then used to accommodate the ligand by reorienting nearby side chains. These residues and the ligand are then minimized. Finally, each ligand is re docked into its corresponding low energy protein structures and the resulting complexes are ranked according to a scoring function combining Glide Score and Prime energies.

Schrodinger software

Induced fit docking was performed using Schrodinger software. Virtual screening has proven to be a very successful approach for finding ligand hits and assisting lead optimization in structure-based drug discovery projects. By docking a large library of compounds into one or more high-resolution structures of the target receptor, fewer compounds typically need to be experimentally screened to identify prospective lead optimization candidates. Beyond identifying small molecules likely to bind well to a protein target, docking methods are used in a variety of context such as polypeptide and macrocycle pose prediction, predicting protein-ligand complex geometries, and preparing congeneric series for binding affinity prediction with methods such as Free Energy Perturbation or MM-GBSA. Moving beyond the rigid receptor approximation common in structure-based virtual screening, the Induced Fit docking protocol predicts the effect of ligand docking on protein structure. In the present study Schrodinger mastero11.1 version was used for induced fit docking.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the present study, molecular docking studies have been carried out with the secondary metabolites present in the entomopathogenic fungi *B. bassiana* with the important protein present in the rice moth *C. cephalonica*. This study enables us to know about the microbial genome and the allelochemicals that can bind with the insect protein.

Once the process was completed, it gave a docked structure indicating the corresponding E-values. More the negative E- value, more efficient is the docking process. The Glide score, Glide energy, hydrogen bond interaction were performed using Schrodinger software.

Conversion of 2D structures to 3D structure

Plate 1: 2D structure of Beauveriolide I.

Plate 2: 3D structure of Beauveriolide I.

a. Bassianolide

b. Beauvericin

c. Beauveriolide IV

a. Bassianolide**b. Beauvericin****c. Beauveriolide IV****d. Beauveriolide V****e. Beauveriolide I****f. Beauveriolide III****Plate 5: 3D Structure of secondary metabolites found in *B. bassiana*.**

g. Oosporein

h. Tenellin

Plate 6: 3D Structure of secondary metabolites found in *B. bassiana*.

Confirmation

In signal transduction networks, the fine tuning of signalling targets and the requirement of alternative pathways ensuring the robustness of the response require conformational flexibility of the binding sites. Conformational fluctuations are not restricted to the nano- and Pico second range, but also occur in the range of milliseconds to seconds (or even hours), where they probably affect signalling steps (Wu *et al.*, 2009 and Xing and Chen 2008). This conformational dynamism opens the way for a large involvement of conformational selection in signalling-related binding events (Gsponer *et al.*, 2008; Smock and Gierasch, (2009).

SEQUENCE USED: TARGET PROTEIN

Hexamerin receptor [*Corcyra cephalonica*] GenBank: ADA84299.1

MGLRSRKVLWMVKMVILVMLLTVATASVVPDDSKVLITKEPMVNLD
 VKTKELFILKLLNHILQPSLYEDIRSIAREYTIEDNMDKYVKVEVVKAFIT
 YKLGMLPRGEVFDMDVKQAEEAIKVFQLLYFAKDFDIFVRTACWLRE
 RINGGMFVYALTAAVFHRPDCNGISLPAPYEIYPHFFVDSHILHKAFMM
 KMTKASVDAGIKDYYGINVKDNNVVVIDWRKSLRHTMSEFDRTSYFTE
 DIDLNTYFYYLHMSYPYWMSEDIYSVNKERRGETMWYSFHVSTVARR
 YKGYRLPCTTLHPQCEMYHSQKATGRQILLRTGDMPVRCYNVQLITE
 DDIRFKDLIDDDRRYRDAIRKGYIETHDGTTLRLKPDIEYLSRMLLG
 GYVSQENFRWQKGAVPLTLLSYSNYNTNKNTYIPHAVDTFATALRDPG
 AWKLMKKLSEIFILFKNMLPSYTRDEFDFPGVKIEQVSTDKLVTMDEY
 NVDITNAMYLDKTEMQNQRSDMMYVARMHRLNHHPFKVTIEVVSDK
 AVDSVVRVFLGPKIDCMGRFISINDKRNDMVEIDSFLYKLDTGKNTIIRN
 SLEMHNVIQERPLVRGIWERSVDANAGMKRLDNWWYKSRIGFPHRLLL

PIGSIGGTVYEIFRDRNTRTHRFPGAIFRPEYYSTATPLVDGACAWTRCR
VFPTNRPLDEGYLSTHQYEVPPMYHYMCKKFVPVSHPG

HOMOLOGY MODELING

After the target–template alignment, next step in the homology modeling is the model building. A variety of methods can be used to build a protein model for the target. Generally rigid-body assembly, segment matching, spatial restraint, and artificial evolution are used for model building. Rigid body assembly model building relies on the natural dissection of the protein structure into conserved core regions, variable loops that connect them and side chains that decorate the backbone. Model accuracy is based on the template selection and alignment accuracy. Generation of restraints is based upon the assumption the corresponding distances between aligned residues in the template and the target structures are similar (Vyas *et al.*, 2012)

Blast search

Template used

Template: Chain A, Arylphorin [Bombyx mori]

Sequence ID: 3WJM_A

Model designed

Model 1

Totally eight compounds were retrieved from *B. bassiana* and were docked against the target hexamerin receptor protein (Table 1). Beauveriolide V and Tenellin were docked with good binding energy (Table 2) and the same compounds Beauveriolide V and Tenellin had extended hydrogen bond interaction with the target. The compounds extended significant hydrogen bond interaction and extended at the amino acid His 284, Met 279, His 256, Tyr 261 and Tyr 259. Hence the compounds Beauveriolide V and Tenellin could be considered as potentials against the target. This provides substantive evidence that the compounds from entomopathogenic fungi could exert an effective biopesticidal effect to the rice moth.

Recently, an inverse virtual screening (IVS) technology based on molecular docking methods has been developed and widely used for the process of target identification.

Hexamerins essentially participate in the dynamics of amino acid storage and exploitation that occur during insect development. These six sub unit proteins are primarily synthesized by the larval fat body and are massively stored in hemolymph as an amino acid source for development toward the adult stage (Burmester and Scheller 1999).

Manohar *et al.* (2010) have investigated ecdysteroid-mediated expression of hexamerin (arylphorin) in the rice moth, *Corcyra cephalonica*. The hormonal studies were carried out using the normal and the thorax-ligated insects with both 20E and its non-steroidal agonist RH-5992. Rao *et al.* (2016) have studied a riboflavin-binding hexamerin (RbHex) was cloned

and characterized from the larval fat body of *Corcyra cephalonica*. So far, the target protein hexamerin receptor protein has not been docked with the isolated compounds chosen from *B. bassiana* in our study. This forms the first significant report on the inhibition of hexamerin receptor protein activity of *C. cephalonica* confirmed by *insilico* analysis. The process of uptake of hexamerins during metamorphosis from insect haemolymph by fat body cells is reminiscent of receptor-mediated endocytosis.

In the present study secondary metabolites of *B. bassiana* (Beauveriolide V and Tenellin) selected were bind with hexamerin receptor protein of *C. cephalonica* it shows clear outlook about the toxicity of Beauveriolide V and Tenellin to the target *C. cephalonica*.

Docking performed: Induced fit docking

Table 1: Molecular docking interaction of secondary metabolites obtained from *B. bassiana* with hexamerin receptor protein of *C. cephalonica*.

Compound name	Glide rotatable bonds	Glide ligand efficiency	Glide ligand efficiency sa	Glide ligand efficiency ln	Glide gscore	Glide lipo
BeauveriolideV	7	-0.353	-1.109	-2.468	-10.941	-1.008
BeauveriolideIII	7	-0.306	-0.961	-2.139	-9.482	-2.019
BeauveriolideIV	7	-0.298	-0.937	-2.085	-9.243	-1.313
Beauveriolide I	7	-0.21	-0.661	-1.47	-6.52	-2.084
Tenellin.I	9	-0.452	-1.355	-2.838	-12.191	-1.096
Bassianin	9	-0.438	-1.314	-2.752	-11.822	-3.018
Beauvericin	9	-0.424	-1.271	-2.663	-11.439	-1.891

Table 2: Hydrogen bond interaction of *B. bassiana* secondary metabolites with the hexamerin receptor protein of *C. cephalonica*.

S.No	Compound	Hydrogen Bond interaction	Amino acid involved	Bond length
1.	Beauveriolide V.1	C=O...CH	His 284	2.8 Å
2.	Tenellin.1	N-CH...C=O	Met 279	1.8Å
		C-OH...CH	His 256	2.4Å
		C-OH...CH	Tyr 261	2.7Å
		C-OH...C=O	Tyr 259	1.8Å

Plate 7: Docking: 2D interaction profile of Beauveriolide V with the target protein.

Plate 8: Docking: 3D interaction profile of Beauveriolide V with the target protein.

Plate 9: Docking: 2D interaction profile of Tenellin with the target protein.

Plate 10: Docking: 3D interaction profile of Tenellin with the target protein.

Table 3: Docking score and Glide energy of the docked compound.

S.No	Compound	Docking Score (kcal/mol)	H- Bond	Glide energy
1	Beauveriolide V.1	-10.941	1	-51.77
2	Tenellin.1	-12.191	4	-54.486

The docking score between the fungal metabolite Beauveriolide V and the target protein was -10.941kcal/mol and the fungal metabolite Tenellin showed -12.191kcal/mol. The glide energy obtained was about -51.77 for Beauveriolide V and -54.486 for Tenellin (Table 3).

CONCLUSION

The docking is also valid by the formation of hydrogen bond between them. Beauveriolide V docked with one hydrogen bond and Tenellin docked with four hydrogen bonds to the target hexamerin receptor protein. According to Lipinski (2004) rule presence of hydrogen bonding has proved that toxicity of fungal metabolite to the target protein of *C. cephalonica*. From the results it is suggested that *B. bassiana* culture filtrates will be used against the *C. cephalonica* larvae as a biocontrol agent.

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AUTHORS CONTRIBUTION

All authors contributed equally to this manuscript.

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